

Exploring the Mechanisms of Self-Immolation Inhibitor

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ABSTRACT: People in many parts of the globe have recently taken their own life, leaving loved ones behind, as a result of overwhelming mental and emotional pain. Out of all the instances of self-harm that have been recorded from 1987 to 2017, around 17% originate from India. One of the major methods of suicide is to hang oneself from a ceiling fan. This study presents an alternative security setup for roof fans that may prevent instances of self-destructive behaviour. Stress testing was first carried out on all of the current model fans to determine the force exerted by the fan's own load on the down bar. The modification to the roof fan will enhance the strategy in the event of an accident, depending on the results. Instead of a down street, a spring now connects it to the house's roof in this revised design. The spring is designed in a way that its inflexibility causes it to explode under loads greater than the safe load. The person is saved from hanging death when the spring extends and the fan lets down due to the inflexibility disappointment of the spring. Solid Works is used to create the roof fan's computer-aided design (CAD) model, while ANSYS is used for the down pole investigation. However, Solid Works is where the examination of spring assembly takes place.

Keyword: Arduino Uno, GSM Module, Suicide Prevention, Hanging, Buzzer.

I. INTRODUCTION

An enormous global health and financial burden is self-destruction. There are more than one million deaths per year, and hanging is one of the top ten causes of death worldwide. After injuring someone, hanging is the second most common way to end it all in India. An increasing number of people, especially young adults, have taken their own lives by hanging in recent years. A tremendous social, emotional, and financial burden is placed on our society by the fact that 71% of suicides in India occur among those younger than 44 years of age. Developing effective countermeasures is still a challenging task for health professionals in general. It is crucial to have detailed data on the many elements associated with self-destructive hanging in that particular geographical area in order to prevent such suicides. Keeping this in mind, we focused an upcoming study on India in order to identify the various factors connected to tragically self-destructive hanging; in order to demarcate intervention zones. The primary goal of the

assignment is to reduce the self-destruction attempts occurring via roof fan in order to conquer these difficulties. The suggested setup for the project includes a 4*4 lattice keypad, an LCD display, a buzzer, a GSM module, a potentiometer, a spring, and a roof fan. Arduino IDE is the programming language used. The person tries to hang, and the shaft becomes strained and falls. Additionally, the alarm is activated and the message is sent to the designated watchmen via GSM. The rate of change and progress of the bar may be seen with the help of calculations. Reducing self-destruction attempts occurring by roof fan is the main objective of the endeavour.

II. OBJECTIVE

- [1] To prevent the suicide of a person hanging to the fan.
- [2] To focus on various factors associated with suicide by hanging in India with a view to identify the area of intervention.
- [3] For Energy conservation and system scalability.

III. WORKING METHODOLOGY

The item is certainly not a completely new fan, it is basically a section that must be joined to a standard fan. The customary fan is appended to the rooftop with a clip and it is covered by a cup, here we are just giving the cinch. This clasp has a spring system, on the off chance that somebody over 20 kgs attempts to swing from the fan, the spring basically descends and the fan drops keeping the understudy from hanging. Simultaneously an alarm appended inside the cup likewise goes off, cautioning the authorities. They had tried to connect an alarm also in light of the fact that they didn't need the understudy to evaluate some other strategy for self destruction,

since this didn't work, "If the alarm sounds, that specialists will guarantee that the individual gets help else we just let go of the case. "He likewise added that there were different highlights connected, for example, a cautioning framework that would convey a message to the front work area or straightforwardly to the individual in control and furthermore send data to the closest CCTV camera so the specialists would know where precisely the self destruction endeavor had occurred.

IV. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The proposed project configuration comprises of roof fan with equipment parts of arduino uno, potentiometer, spring ,roof fan, Buzzer, GSM module, LCD show ,4*4 lattice keypad And programming utilized are arduino ide . At whatever point the individual attempts to hang, the shaft gets stretched and descends. Moreover the alert is sounded and GSM sends the message to the specific watchmen. Given the assistance of calculation the speed and development of the bar is observed. The primary target of the venture is to diminish the self-destruction endeavors happening through roof fan.

V. HARDWARE DESCRIPTION

The hardware components are used in this project is described below.

A. ARDUINO UNO

The Arduino UNO is the best board to begin

with gadgets and coding. In the event that this is your first experience fiddling with the stage, the UNO is the strongest board you can begin playing with. The UNO is the most utilized and archived leading body of the entire Arduino family. Arduino Uno is a microcontroller board dependent on the ATmega328P (datasheet).

It has 14 computerized input/output pins (of which 6 can be utilized as PWM outputs), 6 simple information sources, a 16 MHz ceramic resonator (CSTCE16M0V53-R0), a USB association, a force jack, an ICSP header and a reset button. It contains all that expected to help the microcontroller; essentially interface it to a PC with a USB link or force it with an AC-to-DC connector or battery to begin.. You can dabble with your Uno without agonizing a lot over accomplishing something incorrectly, most dire outcome imaginable you can substitute the chip for a couple of dollars and begin once more. "Uno" signifies one in Italian and was picked to check the arrival of Arduino Software (IDE) 1.0. The Uno board and form 1.0 of Arduino Software (IDE) were the reference renditions of Arduino, presently advanced to more up to date delivers.

The Uno board is the first in a progression of USB Arduino sheets, and the reference model for the Arduino stage; for a broad rundown of current, past or obsolete sheets see the Arduino record of sheets.

Tragically, self-destruction is a major financial and health cost on a worldwide scale. Hanging is among the top 10 leading causes of death globally, accounting for over one million annual fatalities. In India, wounding someone is the most prevalent means of suicide, followed by hanging. Suicide by hanging has been on the rise in recent years, particularly among young adults. Our society bears a heavy social, emotional, and financial weight due to the fact that 71% of suicides in India happen among individuals younger than 44 years of age. As a whole, health care providers still face the formidable challenge of developing effective countermeasures. If we want to stop people in that region from self-destructively hanging themselves, we need comprehensive data on all the factors that contribute to this problem. For this reason, we want to conduct

a research on India in the near future to determine what variables

about the sad self-harming act of hanging; to establish intervention zones. In order to overcome these challenges, the main objective of the project is to decrease the number of attempts at self-destruction using the roof fan. It is recommended that you use a 4*4 lattice keypad, an LCD screen, a buzzer, a GSM module, a potentiometer, a spring, and a roof fan for this project. One of the languages utilised is Arduino IDE. As the individual attempts to dangle, the shaft strains and eventually breaks. Also, the selected watchmen get a message via GSM and the alarm is triggered. Calculations may show the rate of change and progress of the bar. A primary goal of the initiative is to decrease the number of roof fan suicide attempts.

B. GSM MODULE

GSM is a portable correspondence modem; it represents worldwide framework for versatile

correspondence (GSM). The possibility of GSM was created at Bell Laboratories in 1970. It is a broadly utilized versatile correspondence framework on the planet. GSM is an open and advanced cell innovation utilized for sending versatile voice and information administrations work at the 850MHz, 900MHz, 1800MHz, and 1900MHz recurrence bands. GSM innovation was created as a computerized framework utilizing the time division different access (TDMA) method for correspondence purposes.

A GSM digitizes and lessens the information, at that point sends it down through a channel with two unique floods of customer information, each in its own specific schedule

opening. The computerized framework can convey 64 kbps to 120 Mbps of information rates. There are different cell sizes in a GSM framework like full scale, miniature, pico, and umbrella cells. Every cell fluctuates according to the execution area. There are five distinctive cell sizes in a GSM network full scale, miniature, pico, and umbrella cells. The inclusion zone of every cell differs as indicated by the execution climate.

The time division various access (TDMA) procedure depends on allocating diverse time allotments to every client on a similar recurrence. It can without much of a stretch adjust to information transmission and voice correspondence and can convey 64kbps to 120Mbps of information rate.

C. LCD DISPLAY

Compact disc (Liquid Crystal Display) is a sort of level board show which utilizes fluid gems in its essential type of activity. LEDs have an enormous and differing set of utilization cases for buyers and organizations, as they can be normally found

in cell phones, TVs, PC screens and instrument boards. LCDs were a major jump regarding the innovation they supplanted, which incorporate light-transmitting diode (LED) and gas-plasma shows. LCDs permitted showcases to be a lot more slender than cathode beam tube (CRT) innovation. LCDs devour significantly less force than LED and gas-show shows since they work on the guideline of hindering light as opposed to emanating it. Where a LED emanates light, the fluid precious stones in a LCD deliver a picture utilizing a backdrop illumination. As LCDs have supplanted more established presentation advances, LCDs have started being supplanted by new showcase innovations, for example, OLEDs. A show is comprised of millions of pixels. The nature of a presentation usually alludes to the quantity of pixels; for instance, a 4K showcase is comprised of 3840 x2160 or 4096x2160 pixels. A pixel is comprised of three subpixels; a red, blue and green—normally called RGB. At the point when the subpixels in a pixel change shading mixes, an alternate tone can be created. With every one of the pixels on a showcase cooperating, the presentation can make a huge number of various tones. At the point when the pixels are quickly turned on and off, an image is made.

The manner in which a pixel is controlled is diverse in each kind of show; CRT, LED, LCD and fresher sorts of showcases all control pixels in an unexpected way. To put it plainly, LCDs are lit by a backdrop illumination, and pixels are turned here and there electronically while utilizing fluid precious stones to pivot spellbound light. A polarizing glass channel is put in front and behind every one of the pixels, the front channel is set at 90 degrees. In the middle of the two channels are the fluid precious stones, which can be electronically turned on and off. LCDs are made with either an inactive lattice or a functioning framework show matrix. The dynamic lattice LCD is otherwise called a slim film semiconductor (TFT) show. The aloof network LCD has a framework of conductors with pixels situated at every convergence in the matrix. A current is sent across two conductors on the network to control the light for any pixel.

A functioning network has a semiconductor situated at every pixel convergence,

E. BUZZER

A buzzer or beeper is a sound flagging device,[1] which might be mechanical, electromechanical, or piezoelectric (piezo for short). Run of the mill employments of signals and beepers incorporate alert gadgets, clocks, and affirmation of client information,

requiring less current to control the

luminance of a pixel. Hence, the current in a functioning lattice show can be turned here and there more oftentimes, improving the screen revive time. Some inactive framework LCD's have double checking, implying that they filter the network twice with current in the very time that it took for one output in the first innovation. In any case, dynamic grid is as yet an unrivaled innovation out of the two.

D. SPRING

The spring hangs in a relaxed, unstretched position. If you were to hold the bottom of the spring and pull downward, the spring would stretch. If you were to pull with just a little force, the spring would stretch just a little bit. And if you were to pull with a much greater force, the spring would stretch a much greater extent.

for example, a mouse snap or keystroke.

F. CEILING FAN

The roof fan has an engine that changes over electrical energy into mechanical energy. To begin with, the capacitor of the roof fan forces up the electric engine, in this manner

G. BATTERY

H. SERVO MOTOR

A servo engine is a sort of engine that can turn with extraordinary accuracy. Regularly this sort of engine comprises of a control circuit that gives input on the current situation of the engine shaft, this criticism permits the servo engines to pivot with incredible accuracy.

I. POTENTIOMETER

A **potentiometer** is a three-terminal resistor with a sliding or rotating contact that forms an adjustable voltage divider. If only two

making it start and run. As the electrical flow arrives at the engine, it enters curls of wire that are folded over a metal base. At the point when this current goes through the wire, it makes an attractive field which further applies power in a

clockwise movement. Thusly, the electric energy is changed over into mechanical energy and makes the engine curls turn. The edges joined to the engine additionally turn over acquiring movement with the turning of the loops.

A **battery** is a source of energy which provides a push - a voltage - of energy to get the current flowing in a **circuit**. A bulb uses the electrical energy provided by the **battery**, but does not use current. When the energy in the **battery** is used up there is no current and the bulb does not light up.

terminals are used, one end and the wiper, it acts as a variable resistor or rheostat.

J. 4*4 MATRIX KEYPAD

This 16-button keypad provides a useful human interface component for microcontroller projects. Convenient adhesive backing provides a simple way to mount the keypad in a variety of applications. The Keypad 4x4 features a total of 16 buttons in Matrix form. This is a membrane keypad with no moving parts. It has a nice overlay depicting a telephone type keypad with additional four functional buttons. A female 8-pin berg connector is provided for interfacing it with your microcontroller circuits.

VI. CONCLUSION

Since self-destruction is a complex problem with many facets, efforts to combat it should also be multifaceted. To design and

implement a public arrangement that is fiscally prudent, appropriate, and responsive to the needs of the community, it is anticipated that everyone will work together, coordinate, collaborate, and take responsibility. Rather from being seen as a traditional mental health practice, self-destruction prevention is more of a social and general wellness goal in India. This is the perfect time for

mental health professionals to take the lead in the fight against suicide and save the lives of thousands of young Indians.

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